

Mixed Model Analysis

[DataSet1] /Users/atom/Library/Mobile Documents/com~apple~CloudDocs/Desktop/PhD Docs/Main study/OWM_1.2.sav

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_b	1		1
	Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_w	1		1
	Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_b	1		1
	Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_w	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		10		12

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_b		
	Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_w		
	Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_b		
	Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_w		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	572.709659
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	584.709659
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	584.923400
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	614.658447
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	608.658447

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	21.404	1263.115	<.001
Patient	1	18.417	14630.272	<.001
Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_b	1	18.945	.711	.410
Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_w	1	22.904	1.867	.185
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_b	1	23.647	33.352	<.001
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_w	1	186.075	120.064	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	3.816	.107	21.404	35.540	<.001	3.593
Patient	3.983	.033	18.417	120.956	<.001	3.914
Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_ b	.264	.313	18.945	.843	.410	-.391
Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_ w	-.384	.281	22.904	-1.366	.185	-.964
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_ b	.525	.091	23.647	5.775	<.001	.337
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_ w	.492	.045	186.075	10.957	<.001	.404

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ... Upper Bound
Doctor	4.039
Patient	4.053
Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_ b	.918
Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_ w	.197
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_ b	.712
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_ w	.581

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.126	.013	9.577	<.001	.103
	Var(2)	.384	.040	9.601	<.001	.313
	Corr(2,1)	.129	.073	1.773	.076	-.015
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.076	.042	1.826	.068	.026
	Var(2)	.005	.006	.772	.440	.000
	Corr(2,1)	-.483	.653	-.740	.459	-.976

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter	95% ...	
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.155
	Var(2)	.471
	Corr(2,1)	.268
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.223
	Var(2)	.059
	Corr(2,1)	.815

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * BenevolenceParticular_b	1		1
	Doctor * BenevolenceParticular_w	1		1
	Patient * BenevolenceParticular_b	1		1
	Patient * BenevolenceParticular_w	1		1
	Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		10		12

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * BenevolenceParticular_b		
	Doctor * BenevolenceParticular_w		
	Patient * BenevolenceParticular_b		
	Patient * BenevolenceParticular_w		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	606.884175
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	618.884175
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	619.097915
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	648.832962
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	642.832962

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	18.555	1935.400	<.001
Patient	1	16.759	11739.745	<.001
Doctor * BenevolenceParticular_b	1	23.764	.429	.519
Doctor * BenevolenceParticular_w	1	39.635	1.734	.196
Patient * BenevolenceParticular_b	1	25.006	14.409	<.001
Patient * BenevolenceParticular_w	1	199.393	68.377	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	3.863	.088	18.555	43.993	<.001	3.679
Patient	4.062	.037	16.759	108.350	<.001	3.983
Doctor * BenevolenceParticular_b	.201	.307	23.764	.655	.519	-.432
Doctor * BenevolenceParticular_w	-.391	.297	39.635	-1.317	.196	-.993
Patient * BenevolenceParticular_b	.389	.103	25.006	3.796	<.001	.178
Patient * BenevolenceParticular_w	.374	.045	199.393	8.269	<.001	.285

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ...
	Upper Bound
Doctor	4.047
Patient	4.141
Doctor * BenevolenceParticular_b	.834
Doctor * BenevolenceParticular_w	.210
Patient * BenevolenceParticular_b	.600
Patient * BenevolenceParticular_w	.463

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.147	.015	9.649	<.001	.120
	Var(2)	.385	.040	9.595	<.001	.314
	Corr(2,1)	.110	.073	1.508	.132	-.034
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.072	.041	1.773	.076	.024
	Var(2)	.010	.008	1.238	.216	.002
	Corr(2,1)	-.251	.522	-.481	.631	-.874

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ...
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.180
	Var(2)	.473
	Corr(2,1)	.250
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.217
	Var(2)	.049
	Corr(2,1)	.683

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * IntegrityParticular_b	1		1
	Doctor * IntegrityParticular_w	1		1
	Patient * IntegrityParticular_b	1		1
	Patient * IntegrityParticular_w	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		10		12

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * IntegrityParticular_b		
	Doctor * IntegrityParticular_w		
	Patient * IntegrityParticular_b		
	Patient * IntegrityParticular_w		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	586.883259
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	598.883259
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	599.097000
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	628.832047
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	622.832047

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	14.718	2534.268	<.001
Patient	1	13.814	15709.814	<.001
Doctor * IntegrityParticular_b	1	20.987	.712	.408
Doctor * IntegrityParticular_w	1	20.519	3.058	.095
Patient * IntegrityParticular_b	1	29.436	19.801	<.001
Patient * IntegrityParticular_w	1	179.722	97.485	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	3.920	.078	14.718	50.342	<.001	3.753
Patient	4.110	.033	13.814	125.339	<.001	4.039
Doctor * IntegrityParticular_b	.235	.279	20.987	.844	.408	-.345
Doctor * IntegrityParticular_w	-.378	.216	20.519	-1.749	.095	-.828
Patient * IntegrityParticular_b	.422	.095	29.436	4.450	<.001	.228
Patient * IntegrityParticular_w	.404	.041	179.722	9.873	<.001	.323

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ...
	Upper Bound
Doctor	4.086
Patient	4.180
Doctor * IntegrityParticular_b	.815
Doctor * IntegrityParticular_w	.072
Patient * IntegrityParticular_b	.616
Patient * IntegrityParticular_w	.485

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.136	.014	9.601	<.001	.111
	Var(2)	.384	.040	9.608	<.001	.313
	Corr(2,1)	.156	.072	2.168	.030	.013
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.070	.039	1.786	.074	.023
	Var(2)	.006	.007	.935	.350	.001
	Corr(2,1)	-.577	.578	-.998	.318	-.982

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ...
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.167
	Var(2)	.471
	Corr(2,1)	.293
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.209
	Var(2)	.052
	Corr(2,1)	.777

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * CompetenceParticular_b	1		1
	Doctor * CompetenceParticular_w	1		1
	Patient * CompetenceParticular_b	1		1
	Patient * CompetenceParticular_w	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		10		12

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * CompetenceParticular_b		
	Doctor * CompetenceParticular_w		
	Patient * CompetenceParticular_b		
	Patient * CompetenceParticular_w		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	595.644223
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	607.644223
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	607.857963
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	637.593010
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	631.593010

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	21.531	321.468	<.001
Patient	1	201.801	10052.167	<.001
Doctor * CompetenceParticular_b	1	17.354	.260	.616
Doctor * CompetenceParticular_w	1	20.355	.258	.617
Patient * CompetenceParticular_b	1	201.195	51.543	<.001
Patient * CompetenceParticular_w	1	200.480	92.126	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	3.812	.213	21.531	17.930	<.001	3.371
Patient	3.866	.039	201.801	100.260	<.001	3.790
Doctor * CompetenceParticular_b	.164	.322	17.354	.510	.616	-.514
Doctor * CompetenceParticular_w	-.162	.319	20.355	-.508	.617	-.826
Patient * CompetenceParticular_b	.475	.066	201.195	7.179	<.001	.345
Patient * CompetenceParticular_w	.405	.042	200.480	9.598	<.001	.322

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ...
	Upper Bound
Doctor	4.254
Patient	3.942
Doctor * CompetenceParticular_b	.842
Doctor * CompetenceParticular_w	.502
Patient * CompetenceParticular_b	.606
Patient * CompetenceParticular_w	.488

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.144	.014	9.999	<.001	.118
	Var(2)	.383	.040	9.626	<.001	.313
	Corr(2,1)	.140	.073	1.926	.054	-.004
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.091	.047	1.935	.053	.033
	Var(2)	.000 ^b	.000	.	.	.
	Corr(2,1)	.042 ^b	.000	.	.	.

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ...
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.175
	Var(2)	.470
	Corr(2,1)	.278
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.250
	Var(2)	.
	Corr(2,1)	.

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

b. This covariance parameter is redundant. The test statistic and confidence interval cannot be computed.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * Trust_b	1		1
	Doctor * Trust_w	1		1
	Patient * Trust_b	1		1
	Patient * Trust_w	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		10		12

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * Trust_b		
	Doctor * Trust_w		
	Patient * Trust_b		
	Patient * Trust_w		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	670.312922
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	682.312922
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	682.526663
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	712.261710
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	706.261710

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	14.569	1372.356	<.001
Patient	1	202.203	16981.451	<.001
Doctor * Trust_b	1	16.012	3.417	.083
Doctor * Trust_w	1	186.470	28.425	<.001
Patient * Trust_b	1	201.768	26.525	<.001
Patient * Trust_w	1	200.389	100.099	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	4.181	.113	14.569	37.045	<.001	3.940
Patient	4.586	.035	202.203	130.313	<.001	4.517
Doctor * Trust_b	.943	.510	16.012	1.848	.083	-.138
Doctor * Trust_w	.351	.066	186.470	5.331	<.001	.221
Patient * Trust_b	.903	.175	201.768	5.150	<.001	.557
Patient * Trust_w	.767	.077	200.389	10.005	<.001	.616

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ... Upper Bound
Doctor	4.422
Patient	4.655
Doctor * Trust_b	2.024
Doctor * Trust_w	.481
Patient * Trust_b	1.249
Patient * Trust_w	.919

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.241	.024	9.997	<.001	.198
	Var(2)	.314	.033	9.579	<.001	.256
	Corr(2,1)	.112	.073	1.532	.126	-.033
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.179	.077	2.320	.020	.077
	Var(2)	.000	.001	.128	.898	2.509E-11
	Corr(2,1)	-1.000 ^b	.000	.	.	.

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ... Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.294
	Var(2)	.385
	Corr(2,1)	.252
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.417
	Var(2)	506.093
	Corr(2,1)	.

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction.

b. This covariance parameter is redundant. The test statistic and confidence interval cannot be computed.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * Trust_b	1		1
	Doctor * Trust_w	1		1
	Patient * Trust_b	1		1
	Patient * Trust_w	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		10		12

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * Trust_b		
	Doctor * Trust_w		
	Patient * Trust_b		
	Patient * Trust_w		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	685.139913
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	697.139913
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	697.353653
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	727.088700
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	721.088700

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	17.662	3469.927	<.001
Patient	1	199.450	18267.760	<.001
Doctor * Trust_b	1	22.004	3.919	.060
Doctor * Trust_w	1	193.293	86.861	<.001
Patient * Trust_b	1	199.322	17.779	<.001
Patient * Trust_w	1	199.879	50.201	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	4.293	.073	17.662	58.906	<.001	4.140
Patient	4.656	.034	199.450	135.158	<.001	4.588
Doctor * Trust_b	.679	.343	22.004	1.980	.060	-.032
Doctor * Trust_w	.671	.072	193.293	9.320	<.001	.529
Patient * Trust_b	.724	.172	199.322	4.216	<.001	.385
Patient * Trust_w	.519	.073	199.879	7.085	<.001	.375

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ... Upper Bound
Doctor	4.446
Patient	4.724
Doctor * Trust_b	1.391
Doctor * Trust_w	.813
Patient * Trust_b	1.063
Patient * Trust_w	.664

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.233	.023	9.961	<.001	.191
	Var(2)	.404	.042	9.668	<.001	.330
	Corr(2,1)	.265	.071	3.758	<.001	.122
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.051	.029	1.775	.076	.017
	Var(2)	6.291E-6	.000	.030	.976	6.598E-34
	Corr(2,1)	-1.000 ^b	.000	.	.	.

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% Confidence . Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.284
	Var(2)	.495
	Corr(2,1)	.397
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.153
	Var(2)	5.998E+22
	Corr(2,1)	.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

b. This covariance parameter is redundant. The test statistic and confidence interval cannot be computed.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * Trust_b	1		1
	Doctor * Trust_w	1		1
	Patient * Trust_b	1		1
	Patient * Trust_w	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		10		12

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * Trust_b		
	Doctor * Trust_w		
	Patient * Trust_b		
	Patient * Trust_w		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Involvement.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	729.703359
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	741.703359
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	741.917099
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	771.652146
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	765.652146

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Involvement.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	59.977	7069.843	<.001
Patient	1	.576	7544.790	.048
Doctor * Trust_b	1	79.956	10.384	.002
Doctor * Trust_w	1	199.848	176.067	<.001
Patient * Trust_b	1	.741	16.497	.218
Patient * Trust_w	1	86.016	37.123	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Involvement.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	3.937	.047	59.977	84.082	<.001	3.843
Patient	4.635	.053	.576	86.861	.048	.293
Doctor * Trust_b	.750	.233	79.956	3.222	.002	.287
Doctor * Trust_w	.981	.074	199.848	13.269	<.001	.836
Patient * Trust_b	1.036	.255	.741	4.062	.218	-6.609
Patient * Trust_w	.510	.084	86.016	6.093	<.001	.344

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ... Upper Bound
Doctor	4.030
Patient	8.978
Doctor * Trust_b	1.213
Doctor * Trust_w	1.127
Patient * Trust_b	8.681
Patient * Trust_w	.676

a. Dependent Variable: Involvement.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.270	.028	9.499	<.001	.220
	Var(2)	.417	.042	9.970	<.001	.343
	Corr(2,1)	.096	.074	1.309	.190	-.049
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.001	.006	.268	.788	9.984E-7
	Var(2)	.022	.020	1.141	.254	.004
	Corr(2,1)	1.000 ^b	.000	.	.	.

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ... Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.332
	Var(2)	.508
	Corr(2,1)	.238
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	2.203
	Var(2)	.125
	Corr(2,1)	.

a. Dependent Variable: Involvement.

b. This covariance parameter is redundant. The test statistic and confidence interval cannot be computed.

Mixed Model Analysis

[DataSet1] /Users/atom/Library/Mobile Documents/com~apple~CloudDocs/Desktop/PhD Docs/Main study/OWM_1.2.sav

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * Communication_b	1		1
	Doctor * Communication_w	1		1
	Patient * Communication_b	1		1
	Patient * Communication_w	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		10		12

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * Communication_b		
	Doctor * Communication_w		
	Patient * Communication_b		
	Patient * Communication_w		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	598.963790
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	610.963790
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	611.177531
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	640.912577
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	634.912577

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	15.196	1867.995	<.001
Patient	1	210.655	16527.741	<.001
Doctor * Communication_b	1	16.168	4.224	.056
Doctor * Communication_w	1	194.362	106.189	<.001
Patient * Communication_b	1	209.987	30.817	<.001
Patient * Communication_w	1	200.037	121.325	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	4.225	.098	15.196	43.220	<.001	4.017
Patient	4.552	.035	210.655	128.560	<.001	4.482
Doctor * Communication_b	.794	.386	16.168	2.055	.056	-.024
Doctor * Communication_w	1.022	.099	194.362	10.305	<.001	.827
Patient * Communication_b	.830	.150	209.987	5.551	<.001	.536
Patient * Communication_w	.752	.068	200.037	11.015	<.001	.617

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ...
	Upper Bound
Doctor	4.433
Patient	4.622
Doctor * Communication_t	1.612
Doctor * Communication_v	1.218
Patient * Communication_t	1.125
Patient * Communication_v	.887

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.229	.023	9.995	<.001	.188
	Var(2)	.228	.024	9.573	<.001	.186
	Corr(2,1)	.026	.074	.356	.722	-.118
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.141	.060	2.358	.018	.062
	Var(2)	.001	.003	.371	.711	4.804E-6
	Corr(2,1)	1.000 ^b	.000	.	.	.

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ...
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.278
	Var(2)	.280
	Corr(2,1)	.169
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.325
	Var(2)	.186
	Corr(2,1)	.

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction.

b. This covariance parameter is redundant. The test statistic and confidence interval cannot be computed.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * Communication_b	1		1
	Doctor * Communication_w	1		1
	Patient * Communication_b	1		1
	Patient * Communication_w	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		10		12

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * Communication_b		
	Doctor * Communication_w		
	Patient * Communication_b		
	Patient * Communication_w		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	705.443299
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	717.443299
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	717.657039
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	747.392086
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	741.392086

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	16.405	3165.148	<.001
Patient	1	52.355	13581.480	<.001
Doctor * Communication_b	1	19.477	.385	.542
Doctor * Communication_w	1	206.507	39.763	<.001
Patient * Communication_b	1	64.246	8.865	.004
Patient * Communication_w	1	200.183	75.911	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	4.300	.076	16.405	56.260	<.001	4.138
Patient	4.618	.040	52.355	116.540	<.001	4.539
Doctor * Communication_b	.193	.312	19.477	.621	.542	-.458
Doctor * Communication_w	.836	.133	206.507	6.306	<.001	.575
Patient * Communication_b	.488	.164	64.246	2.977	.004	.161
Patient * Communication_w	.557	.064	200.183	8.713	<.001	.431

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ...
	Upper Bound
Doctor	4.461
Patient	4.698
Doctor * Communication_t	.844
Doctor * Communication_v	1.098
Patient * Communication_t	.815
Patient * Communication_v	.683

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.214	.022	9.822	<.001	.175
	Var(2)	.490	.051	9.651	<.001	.400
	Corr(2,1)	.263	.069	3.832	<.001	.124
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.052	.035	1.502	.133	.014
	Var(2)	.007	.008	.896	.370	.001
	Corr(2,1)	1.000 ^b	.000	.	.	.

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ...
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.261
	Var(2)	.601
	Corr(2,1)	.392
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.192
	Var(2)	.065
	Corr(2,1)	.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

b. This covariance parameter is redundant. The test statistic and confidence interval cannot be computed.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * Communication_b	1		1
	Doctor * Communication_w	1		1
	Patient * Communication_b	1		1
	Patient * Communication_w	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		10		12

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * Communication_b		
	Doctor * Communication_w		
	Patient * Communication_b		
	Patient * Communication_w		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Involvement.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	854.077714
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	866.077714
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	866.291455
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	896.026501
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	890.026501

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Involvement.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	10.589	2728.380	<.001
Patient	1	8.904	7149.209	<.001
Doctor * Communication_b	1	13.208	.872	.367
Doctor * Communication_w	1	156.979	25.377	<.001
Patient * Communication_b	1	10.761	8.719	.013
Patient * Communication_w	1	198.321	17.902	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Involvement.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	3.927	.075	10.589	52.234	<.001	3.761
Patient	4.618	.055	8.904	84.553	<.001	4.494
Doctor * Communication_b	.292	.312	13.208	.934	.367	-.382
Doctor * Communication_w	.798	.158	156.979	5.038	<.001	.485
Patient * Communication_b	.657	.223	10.761	2.953	.013	.166
Patient * Communication_w	.332	.078	198.321	4.231	<.001	.177

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ...
	Upper Bound
Doctor	4.094
Patient	4.741
Doctor * Communication_t	.966
Doctor * Communication_v	1.111
Patient * Communication_t	1.149
Patient * Communication_v	.486

a. Dependent Variable: Involvement.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.300	.032	9.342	<.001	.243
	Var(2)	.714	.076	9.438	<.001	.580
	Corr(2,1)	.198	.072	2.747	.006	.054
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.028	.041	.689	.491	.002
	Var(2)	.023	.024	.947	.344	.003
	Corr(2,1)	.871	.689	1.263	.207	-1.000

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ...
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.370
	Var(2)	.879
	Corr(2,1)	.335
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.489
	Var(2)	.180
	Corr(2,1)	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Involvement.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * Communication_b	1		1
	Doctor * Communication_w	1		1
	Patient * Communication_b	1		1
	Patient * Communication_w	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		10		12

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * Communication_b		
	Doctor * Communication_w		
	Patient * Communication_b		
	Patient * Communication_w		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	562.081448
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	574.081448
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	574.295188
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	604.030235
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	598.030235

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	14.503	2596.250	<.001
Patient	1	16.496	11099.442	<.001
Doctor * Communication_b	1	16.374	1.144	.300
Doctor * Communication_w	1	199.815	37.184	<.001
Patient * Communication_b	1	19.621	10.268	.005
Patient * Communication_w	1	199.685	80.611	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	3.992	.078	14.503	50.953	<.001	3.824
Patient	4.063	.039	16.496	105.354	<.001	3.981
Doctor * Communication_b	.337	.315	16.374	1.070	.300	-.329
Doctor * Communication_w	.698	.114	199.815	6.098	<.001	.472
Patient * Communication_b	.503	.157	19.621	3.204	.005	.175
Patient * Communication_w	.493	.055	199.685	8.978	<.001	.385

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ...
	Upper Bound
Doctor	4.159
Patient	4.144
Doctor * Communication_t	1.003
Doctor * Communication_v	.923
Patient * Communication_t	.830
Patient * Communication_v	.601

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.139	.014	9.653	<.001	.114
	Var(2)	.315	.033	9.567	<.001	.257
	Corr(2,1)	.040	.074	.547	.584	-.104
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.074	.039	1.880	.060	.026
	Var(2)	.012	.009	1.404	.160	.003
	Corr(2,1)	.074	.442	.167	.868	-.662

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ...
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.170
	Var(2)	.387
	Corr(2,1)	.183
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.209
	Var(2)	.049
	Corr(2,1)	.737

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * Trust_b	1		1
	Doctor * Trust_w	1		1
	Patient * Trust_b	1		1
	Patient * Trust_w	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		10		12

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * Trust_b		
	Doctor * Trust_w		
	Patient * Trust_b		
	Patient * Trust_w		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Communication.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	379.893266
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	391.893266
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	392.107007
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	421.842054
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	415.842054

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Communication.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	15.632	1725.873	<.001
Patient	1	10.798	15366.017	<.001
Doctor * Trust_b	1	16.256	2.196	.157
Doctor * Trust_w	1	184.368	37.992	<.001
Patient * Trust_b	1	14.067	21.080	<.001
Patient * Trust_w	1	198.986	67.300	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Communication.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	4.214	.101	15.632	41.544	<.001	3.999
Patient	4.363	.035	10.798	123.960	<.001	4.286
Doctor * Trust_b	.670	.452	16.256	1.482	.157	-.287
Doctor * Trust_w	.223	.036	184.368	6.164	<.001	.152
Patient * Trust_b	.790	.172	14.067	4.591	<.001	.421
Patient * Trust_w	.524	.064	198.986	8.204	<.001	.398

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ... Upper Bound
Doctor	4.430
Patient	4.441
Doctor * Trust_b	1.626
Doctor * Trust_w	.295
Patient * Trust_b	1.158
Patient * Trust_w	.650

a. Dependent Variable: Communication.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.170	.018	9.508	<.001	.138
	Var(2)	.100	.010	9.569	<.001	.081
	Corr(2,1)	.260	.071	3.631	<.001	.115
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.159	.060	2.639	.008	.076
	Var(2)	.006	.008	.668	.504	.000
	Corr(2,1)	-.162	.561	-.288	.773	-.860

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ... Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.209
	Var(2)	.122
	Corr(2,1)	.393
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.335
	Var(2)	.105
	Corr(2,1)	.747

a. Dependent Variable: Communication.